

PRINCIPLES OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN IN THE CONTEX OF CLIMATE CHANGE

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Abstract. *The contemporary climate crisis has become a severe threat to humanity. Over the past decade, record-high temperatures have been recorded, leading to an increased frequency of extreme weather events, such as catastrophic wildfires, devastating floods, and intense storms. Since 1992, the United Nations has recognized global warming as a significant threat to humanity and has been striving to foster international cooperation to halt the rise in global temperatures. As climate change increasingly impacts our environment, architects are turning to innovative adaptive design strategies, such as "cool roof" systems, adaptive façades that regulate temperature and natural light (e.g., Trombe walls), green roofs and façades, as well as the reuse and retrofitting of existing buildings. This paper examines these innovative methods in adaptive architecture, which enhance the resilience of buildings and communities to extreme weather events and other climate-related threats.*

Keywords: *adaptive architecture, sustainable design, eco-friendliness, energy efficiency, climate change.*

Introduction

Since the initiation of climate change negotiations in 1990, greenhouse gas emissions have risen by 62%, exacerbating the climate crisis. We are now in a critical race to adapt to a rapidly changing climate, alongside two other global threats: biodiversity loss and environmental pollution. In the coming decades, by 2050, a significant portion of the urban population is expected to face increased risks from extreme heat. Studies indicate that 1.6 billion people across more than 970 cities will regularly experience dangerously high temperatures.

Adaptive architecture, defined by its ability to adjust to changing environmental conditions, presents a promising approach to mitigating the effects of climate change. Recognizing the impact of architecture on our planet is paramount when designing and constructing buildings and cities. The construction sector is responsible for nearly 39% of global annual CO₂ emissions, underscoring the significant influence that material choices and construction methods have on our climate. [1]

Urban development often leads to an increase in temperatures in large cities, creating areas with exceptionally high temperatures known as "urban heat islands." (Table №1)

An urban heat island refers to an urban environment with higher temperatures compared to surrounding rural areas. This phenomenon occurs due to a combination of factors related to microclimate changes caused by urbanization.

Table № 1 The global annual CO2 emissions.

Urban heat islands have detrimental effects on the urban population, including:

- Increased energy consumption for ventilation and air conditioning systems.
- Air pollution and smog formation.
- Higher greenhouse gas emissions.
- Deterioration of water quality at treatment facilities.
- Increased morbidity and mortality related to heat.

Below are steps we can take to enhance architectural resilience:

Main Body: In cities of the Mediterranean and the Middle East, residents have long recognized that white surfaces naturally reflect sunlight, making white clothing more comfortable and white houses cooler. On a typical sunny summer afternoon, a clean white roof, reflecting 80% of sunlight, will remain 30°C cooler than a grey roof that reflects only 20% of the solar radiation. According to the International Energy Agency, well-designed cities could reduce energy consumption for heating and cooling by up to 25% (Picture №1).

(Picture №1) The benefits of "cool roofs" for building owners.

This observation highlights the significant role of surface albedo—the ability of materials to reflect sunlight—in mitigating the urban heat island effect. By incorporating reflective materials and light-colored surfaces, cities can reduce heat absorption, lower temperatures, and enhance overall energy efficiency. The potential of such strategies is particularly important in light of the growing challenges posed by climate change, which exacerbate the need for sustainable urban development and energy conservation. [2]

Thanks to the advancements made by chemical engineers, modern roofing waterproofing materials and systems, predominantly in bright white colors, have been developed and are commonly referred to as "cool roofs." The principle behind their functionality lies in their ability to reflect solar radiation (solar reflectance) and exhibit high thermal emittance (the capacity to absorb, convert, and re-emit energy across a different wavelength range). An example of a material with low thermal emittance is galvanized steel, which, despite its high reflectivity, tends to heat up considerably when exposed to sunlight.

"Cool roofs" are typically applied in a liquid form. These coatings consist of cold-curing polymers, specialized additives, fillers, and reflective pigments in various hues. However, it is well-established that light-colored coatings, particularly those in white, exhibit the highest levels of solar reflectance. The surface temperature of such coatings remains close to that of the ambient air, contributing significantly to the mitigation of the urban heat island effect and reducing the demand for cooling energy.

This technology is widely used both in the construction of new roofs and in the repair and restoration of existing ones, with no need to remove the old covering. "Cool roofs" can be applied to various substrates, such as concrete, metal, rolled bitumen, single-ply polymer membranes, and are suitable for flat, pitched, and domed structures. [3]

The benefits of "cool roofs" for building owners are undeniable:

- Energy savings of up to 15% on building cooling.
- Increased comfort in spaces without air conditioning.
- Reduced heat load on machinery, electronics, and industrial equipment.
- Optimized storage temperatures for food, raw materials, and lubricants.
- Extended roof lifespan due to reduced exposure to ultraviolet rays and temperature-induced structural deformations.
- Lower maintenance and repair costs for rooftop air conditioning units.

Another significant solution for reducing air temperatures in urban environments is the greening of roofs and façades. Green roofs not only help mitigate summer heat but also absorb excess rainwater. Additionally, they can be utilized to host small-scale farms for growing vegetables and fruits.

Green roofs, through the natural processes of dew formation and evaporation, have the ability to cool the urban environment during hot summer months. This is achieved by converting the solar energy absorbed by plants into thermal energy, thereby preventing surface temperature increases.

Furthermore, green roofs contribute to reducing the urban heat island effect by covering dark rooftops, which are primary sources of heat in cities. These roofs intercept solar radiation, thereby decreasing the need for air conditioning and reducing greenhouse gas emissions from power plants.

Green roofs have the potential to reduce indoor temperatures by 2-6°C in comparison to conventional roofing systems. The extent of temperature reduction depends on several factors,

including the size and type of the green roof, the regional climate, as well as the building's design and insulation. (Picture №2)

Beyond their cooling effect, green roofs also enhance air quality. The vegetation on these roofs acts as a natural filter, capturing atmospheric pollutants and contaminants while absorbing harmful gases. This process reduces the emission of particulate matter and dust, thereby minimizing the formation of urban smog.

In this way, green roofs play a vital role in mitigating the impacts of climate change and fostering a healthier, more sustainable urban environment. By lowering ambient temperatures, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and improving air quality, they contribute significantly to the adaptation of urban areas to the increasingly warmer summer conditions. [4]

(Picture №2) Schematic representing the diverse processes involved in green roofs.

To achieve energy savings and create comfortable conditions in cold climates, it is essential to incorporate elements of passive solar heating. One such element is the Trombe wall.

A Trombe wall is a massive, dark-colored wall with external glazing. It absorbs solar heat during the day and gradually releases it at night, thereby reducing the need for heating the building. The Trombe wall is a key component of solar architecture, which aims to minimize heating energy consumption through the use of solar energy. It helps maintain a comfortable indoor temperature without the need for additional heating. [5]

The delay in heat release to the interior depends on the thickness of the Trombe wall:

- With a wall thickness of 20 cm, the heat delay is approximately 5 hours;
- With a wall thickness of 40 cm, the delay is approximately 10-12 hours.

The Trombe wall can be made not only of concrete but also of stone or brick. To enhance heat transfer, special openings are created at the bottom and top of the wall to facilitate natural air convection, and fans are sometimes installed to promote forced circulation for more efficient heat release.

Solar rays pass through the glazing and strike the concrete wall, which is positioned approximately 100 mm away from the glazing. The ultraviolet rays from the sun heat the surface of the wall, and some of the rays are reflected from the wall as infrared radiation, which does not pass through the glass, thereby warming the air as well. (Picture №3)

(Picture №3) The Trombe wall efficiency.

The construction industry, known for its high energy intensity, accounts for up to 39% of global CO₂ emissions, with 28% of this figure attributable solely to the operation of buildings—namely, their heating, cooling, ventilation, and lighting. The remaining 11% is directly linked to the construction process itself. To minimize its ecological impact, a complete reevaluation of construction practices is necessary.

Adaptive architecture is a design approach that allows buildings to adjust to changing conditions and needs throughout their lifecycle. This is a crucial element of sustainable development, as it enhances the flexibility and longevity of buildings while reducing their environmental impact.

Adaptive reuse offers an alternative to demolition, providing an opportunity to improve the energy efficiency of existing structures. While much attention is given to the preservation of architectural heritage, most buildings lack historical significance and are demolished after 30 to 50 years. However, the global environmental crisis compels us to reconsider this approach, urging us to evaluate the "climatic value" of a building on par with its cultural and historical significance. [6]

One of the most prominent examples of adaptive reuse can be found in London, England. The Tate Modern art gallery, once the Bankside power station, was converted by Pritzker Prize-winning architects Jacques Herzog and Pierre de Meuron.

In the context of a changing climate and rapid technological progress, adaptive architecture enables buildings to transform and respond to evolving circumstances, adapting to new functions and conditions in order to maintain their relevance and avoid demolition.

Adaptive architecture, which integrates elements such as passive solar heating, cool roofs, green roofs, Trombe walls, and the adaptive reuse of existing buildings, is of paramount importance in mitigating the effects of climate change and creating a more sustainable built environment. These strategies represent a shift away from traditional construction practices, offering solutions that not only reduce energy consumption but also enhance the resilience of buildings to the challenges posed by a changing climate.

Conclusion. By incorporating passive solar design, such as Trombe walls, buildings can effectively harness the sun's energy for heating while minimizing the need for additional heating systems. Cool roofs and green roofs further reduce the urban heat island effect, improve air quality, and enhance the overall comfort of indoor spaces. Meanwhile, adaptive reuse allows us to breathe new life into existing structures, reducing the need for demolition and conserving valuable resources.

Through these innovative approaches, architects and builders can design buildings that are more adaptable to evolving climate conditions, ensuring that structures remain relevant and functional over time. This approach not only helps mitigate the environmental impact of construction but also contributes to creating healthier and more comfortable living environments.

In the broader context, by focusing on resilience, energy efficiency, and the reduction of environmental footprints, adaptive architecture plays a critical role in shaping cities and communities that are better equipped to face the challenges of climate change. By enhancing the adaptability and sustainability of our built environments, we can pave the way for a more environmentally responsible and livable future, ensuring that the needs of both current and future generations are met.

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